

Do customers care about online ethical standards? The influence of corporate social responsibility on buying decisions in Jordan

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Abstract: The research aimed to study the influence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on buying decisions. Additionally, the paper explored whether customers care about online buying decisions. The research used survey method and extensively relied on secondary sources. Besides a systematic sampling method was used and a population of 250 respondents selected, the structural model adopted partial least squares structural equation model and regression analysis to analyze the constructs. The findings indicated that a significant number of Jordanians prefer the implementation of online ethics. Additionally, the CSR was proved to have a positive correlation on the consumers buying decisions on online shopping. The paper assesses the consumers' buying decisions in Jordan and their rationale for online shopping. Besides, it explores the fundamental tenets of CSR on the internet purchasing in Jordan.

JEL Classifications: M14

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, buying decisions, online shopping

Citation: al Adwan, A., Aladwan, K. V., & Al-Adwan, A. S. (2019). Do customers care about online ethical standards? The influence of corporate social responsibility on buying decisions in Jordan. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 15(4), 560-572.

1. Introduction

Predominantly, CSR is an emblem of every organization that seeks to achieve a competitive advantage over its peers. More importantly, it has a significant impact on the significant decisions made by consumers. Typically, some firms adopt CSR to strengthen their relationship with the community (Wu & Lin, 2014). Therefore, the customers form a critical segment for a firm and other stakeholders in the business. Additionally, CSR is increasingly becoming a subject for organizations due to its immense influence on the environment (Jie & Hasan, 2015). Besides, it involves an epitome of responsibility to the community beyond the ordinary transactions (Wang, Tong, Takeuchi, & George, 2016).

Primarily, consumers make decisions when purchasing various commodities. In essence, consistent development in the business sector has led to numerous trends that have enhanced efficiency. The internet has significantly changed the way organizations and people carry their businesses (Khurana & Mehra, 2015). Broadly, advancements in technology have led to online transactions. Notably, most organizations have resorted to conducting their businesses over the internet. Equally, consumers have followed suit by adopting the online platforms to make their purchases.

Jordan has embraced the use of modern technology to enhance the performance of its operation in various sectors. Remarkably, it has emphasized the importance of CSR

binding the organization's relationship with the consumers, and the community (Ibrahim & Hanefah, 2016). On that note, the primary examples are involving the employees and the community in organizational matters and critical projects that affect numerous stakeholders. Further, the presence of the internet as a tool of transactions has necessitated the use of online business transactions in Jordan. Markedly, the financial business has gained immense support from key stakeholders including the government and the customers. Consequently, the CSR has dominated the economic environment of Jordan. Arguably, the activities of the organization on online business ethics influence the decisions made by various buyers (Elg & Hultman, 2016).

Complex buying is a significant decision exhibited by consumers in various places. Typically, customers tend to involve themselves much when carrying out this type of purchase. For example, it consists of the buying of expensive commodities like motor vehicles, laptops, and machines. On that account, the consumer becomes sensitive and wary over the process of complex buying. Secondly, the dissonance reducing buying trend denotes the significant involvement of the customer in the purchase of a particular product. Further, it usually comprises of a high priced commodity that a customer buys infrequently. Furthermore, dissonance reducing buying behavior involves high consumer involvement.

Thirdly, habitual consumer behavior gets unveiled by the low levels of customer involvement in the product. In most cases, it involves the products with a relatively low price that are frequently purchased by the consumer. An example is salt and matchbox. Finally, variety seeking purchasing comportment involves significant differences between brands. Examples are phones and chips.

Research Aim

This study aims to assess the influence of CSR on buying decisions in Jordan. Remarkably, it would explore the insights behind online business transactions and the role of the consumers in carrying trade over the internet. Remarkably, the research would evaluate various online business ethics. Additionally, a determination would seek to assess whether the consumers care about the prime conscience when carrying their business over the internet. Notably, a comprehensive discussion would enumerate the various examples of CSR in Jordan. Further, the research analyses the significant decisions made by the buyers in Jordan when purchasing commodities online. Mainly, the study explores the fundamental tenets of CSR practices and their rationale for consumers' buying trends.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of CSR on online buying decisions in Jordan?
2. What is the role of subjective norm on online buying decisions in Jordan?
3. What is the effect of ethical policies on online buying decisions in Jordan?
4. What is the influence of consumers' attitudes on online buying decisions in Jordan?
5. What is the impact of internet risks on online buying decisions in Jordan?

Extraordinarily, the theory of planned behavior (TPB) was used to answer the above questions. Moreover, its constructs are more comprehensive and relevant to CSR and the perception of human beings. Besides, TPB has more weight than the theory of reasoned

action (TRA). More importantly, the method of planned behavior enumerates fundamental elements like behavioral intention, attitude, subjective norms, and the perception of a particular group. On that note, this paper examines the rationale of CSR on online buying decisions.

Additionally, it assesses the rationale of the internet structure, online ethical standards, internet risks, and the perception of consumers on online purchasing. Therefore, the significant construct embodies the customers' behavior on E-commerce. Arguably, the subjective norm has a positive rationale for the consumers' perception of online buying decisions.

Fundamentally, the literature review embeds a comprehensive discussion of secondary sources on CSR, online buying decisions, the perception of consumers on ethical practices over the internet. More importantly, the review gives a detailed assessment of the research questions and the facts that support the research gap on the rationale of CSR on online buying decisions in Jordan. Subsequently, the research model evaluates the theoretical perspective of the research. Then, the hypothesis, methodology, discussions, and conclusions ensue. Finally, the analysis comprehends limitations, recommendations, and further studies on the rationale of CSR on consumer buying decisions in Jordan.

2. Literature review and theoretical background

2.1. Corporate social responsibility

CSR is a critical element in various organizations in Jordan. On that note, Al-Daaya researched the CSR situation in Jordan. Remarkably, the study attempted to explore the context of the transformation of CSR and its ensuing stages of evolution in Jordan (Al-Daaya, 2017). The research took place at a time when numerous stakeholders in Jordan had become aware of the significance of the revolution of CSR. Notably, the study found that Jordan is a political country that supports the effective transformation of its economic sector through active involvement of the society in the implementation of significant projects and businesses conducted within its jurisdiction. Additionally, the study found that a substantial number of organizations partially understand the rationale of CSR of the performance of firms through effective buying decisions.

A study carried out in 2016 emphasized on CSR and the board characteristics in the Jordanian banks. A population sample of 147 banks was selected from and studied between 2004 and 2013 (Ghabayen et al., 2016). Further regression analysis was adopted to analyze the data collected from the selected financial institutions. Arguably, the results showed that significant stakeholders including the decision of the board affect the buyer buying decisions.

In 2016, a study was carried out on the market factors that influence the consumers' purchasing attitude towards apartments. Further, the study aimed to assess the Jordanians in Bangladesh and the entire supply chain network between Bangladesh and Jordan. Remarkably, the research explored the rationale of markers on the buying trends (Kamal, et al., 2016). A sample of 200 was selected and questionnaires used to collect data. Conspicuously, the SPSS method was used to analyze the information acquired from the respondents. Finally, the study found that urbanization and scarcity of land are the leading factors in the tremendous cost realized in construction. Moreover, customers were discouraged by the significant expenses attributed to the development of apartments.

Remarkably, Khanfar conducted a study on the impact of promotion mix consumers' buying trends in the mobile sector in Zarqa city, Jordan. Specifically, the research explored the significant tools of marketing including promotion, personal selling, public relations, and advertising (Khanfar, 2016). Notably, questionnaires were used to collect data drawn from the respondents in the mobile sector of Jordan. Finally, the study indicated that there is a useful effect of sales promotion, advertising, personal selling, and public relations on the customers buying decisions.

Mohanad researched the adoption of E-commerce in Jordan 2011. Arguably, insecurity denotes a significant challenge facing buyers and sellers in online transactions (Halaweh, 2011). Further, the study aimed to explore the nature of the security threats on both the customer and the organizational context. Additionally, the qualitative research design was used to help in understanding the perspective of business through the internet. The results indicated that the primary decision-makers including the shareholders and the management of an organization influence the buyer buying decisions.

Research was carried out on the influence of CSR on corporate reputation. Arguably, the study used marketing as a prime model in evaluating the Jordanian communication company (Alzghoul et al., 2016). Majorly, reputation is vital for all organizations. Primarily, the study used questionnaires to collect data from the respondents. On that note, a population sample of 93 got selected from the communication organizations in Jordan. The dimensions emphasized in the study include CSR, corporate responsibility, and marketing. Finally, the results indicated that the organization's reputation determines its success.

Further, when customers buy make buying decisions, they consider the reputability of the company. Additionally, the firm's CSR significantly affects corporate reputation. Furthermore, it is also a critical consideration when formulating a strategy for firms.

CSR is a fundamental principle for online businesses globally. Debatably, globalization has played a crucial role in facilitating CSR (Jamali et al., 2009). Furthermore, managers Lebanon, Jordan, and Syria have taken the lead to implement CSR in their organizations to ensure that the consumers get a significant benefit. The study adopted the Quazi and the O'Brien model to assess the rationale of managerial skills on consumer buying trends through online platforms. The results suggest that CSR should get emphasized by all stakeholders in Lebanon, Jordan, and Syria to improve the reputation of online transactions.

Primarily, CSR has become a crucial aspect in Jordan. Markedly, Jordan has a different technique of implementing CSR activities compared to other countries. Notably, a study was carried out to evaluate the level of CSR in non-financial institutions in Jordan (Alshannag et al., 2016). The objective of the study was to expand the knowledge of companies located in Jordan on CSR. Debatably, the paper evaluates the almanac reports of 164 non-financial institutions. Further, it relied on the global reporting initiative to assess the level of CSR. Finally, the results indicated that the level of CSR disclosure is 34.15 for Jordanian firms.

Notably, online purchasing is an emerging trend that gets practiced globally. On that note, a study was conducted in 2017 to assess the impact of the consumers' lifestyle on the online buying decisions for electronic services in Jordan (Al-Dmour et al., 2017). The study exploited the activities, interests, and opinions theory to assess the purchasing trends

in Jordan. Remarkably, the results indicated that the lifestyle dimensions including interests, events, and beliefs have positive effects on the purchasing power to consumers.

Predominantly, Jordan has embraced development and economic growth within its borders. Some of the elements include e-marketing, information, e-management, and selling. Therefore, the growing population of Jordan has contributed to the sprout of business activities. On that note, a study was conducted in 2011 to assess the business operations of the communication companies in Jordan and their rationale on word of mouth marketing strategies (Zamil, 2011). Supplementary, it explored its correlation on the purchasing power of consumers in the Jordanian market. The findings designated that companies should get concerned about word of mouth as a marketing strategy for consumer purchasing power. Furthermore, a significant number of Jordanian consumers prefer online buying.

Momani studied the impact of the brand dimension on the buying decision of the Jordanians when purchasing the shopping goods. The paper explored various elements including quality, quality, country origin, marketing communications, and historical tradition (Momani, 2015). The study aimed to explore the above attributes and their rationale for the Jordanian consumer in shopping for various commodities. Auxiliary, the field survey on the Jordanian market was conducted and questionnaires used to collect data from the consumers. On that note, 300 surveys got selected and handed to the respondents. Notably, the findings suggested that organizations should focus on adopting suitable marketing strategies to influence consumers' loyalty. Further, the companies should consider improving the customers' perception to improve their return on investment.

2.2. Online risks

Consumers' risk when shopping online is a fundamental concern for every country that wants to improve its business conditions. On that account, the study was conducted on the perceived threat of online shopping in Jordan (Masoud, 2013). The paper discusses the perceived risk as the potential for an adverse effect for seeking the desired upshot from an online platform. The research enumerated various elements of perils in Jordan. They include product, financial, delivery, information, and time risk. Notably, a sample size of 395 was selected from the online shopping consumers in Jordan. Additionally, SPSS was adopted in the methodology together with Amos 18. Remarkably, the study discovered that product risk, financial risk, information risk, and delivery risk adversely affect online purchasing performance. Moreover, the study indicated that the perceived social and time risks have no impact on online shopping behavior in Jordan.

E-commerce has played a significant role in the economy of Jordan. Markedly, a study was done on the factors influencing customers' choices on online purchasing in Jordan (Nabot et al., 2014). Conspicuously, the study found that online businesses in Jordan are rare. Worriedly, the economic environment in Jordan faced numerous challenges that affect the dissemination of online shopping. Moreover, 50 questionnaires were developed and distributed to employee professionals and student representatives. Then, data were analyzed through the statistical package for social software. The results indicated that numerous factors influence the attitude toward online shopping in Jordan. Specifically, they include human resources which depict inadequate experience to navigate the internet

and conduct transactions. Other reasons are the lack of a reliable information technology infrastructure on online payment and delivery strategies.

2.3. Consumers' attitude

Alsmadi researched the attitudes of consumers towards online shopping in Jordan. Arguably, the study explored the factors that affect purchasing behaviour on the internet (Alsmadi, 2002). Additionally, the research discussed the opportunities and challenges affecting the Jordanian consumers when making online purchasing decisions. The study evaluated the customers' attitudes and their rationale on demographic variables. On that account, a sample of 453 got selected. Consequently, the study employed multiple tests including the frequencies, ANOVA, and descriptive statistics. The paper indicated that a significant number of Jordanians could have access to the knowledge of using online platforms. Further, Jordan has a reasonable connection to the internet to facilitate business operations. Nevertheless, security concerns over online platforms became a challenge to a significant number of Jordanians. Additionally, the results indicated that diversities in demographics have no impact on consumers' attitudes when making online purchasing making decisions.

Markedly, the internet has become a significant driver for business operations in Jordan. Debatably, a study was carried out in 2012 to determine the actual behavior of Jordanians when shopping online (Al-Jabari, et al., 2012). The plan assesses the planned behavior of respondents. On that note, a sample of 313 university employees got selected through probability sampling. The results showed that perceived behavior and subject norm have great possessions on intention. Additionally, attitude has a low impact on online buying in Jordan. Lastly, the intention of purchasing decisions on the internet has a positive effect on actual online purchasing behavior.

Aldhmour investigated the pertinent factors affecting the customers' objective to adopt online shopping (Aldhmour, 2016). The study assessed some factors that could affect consumers' perception of internet purchasing. On that note, the technology acceptance model got used in the research. Further two variables including the perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) enhanced a comprehensive analysis of the online platforms for business operations in Jordan. A sample of 300 respondents was selected using simple random sampling. Afterwards, questionnaires were developed and used to collect data. The response rate was about 83%. Moreover, the results got analyzed through the statistical package for social software. Besides, the Amos program helped to analyze the study variables. The findings attested that product involvement has the highest positive influence on the customers' morale towards virtual shopping. Nevertheless, PU and perceived ease of use PEOU do not influence customers' attitudes on online purchasing. Lastly, the results indicated that consumers' morale has a significant rationale on clients' intention to adopt online shopping.

Jordan is among the developing countries that embrace the use of the internet to conduct business. On that account, the study adopted a survey method to analyze online shopping in Jordan (Masarweh et al., 2016). Further, the questionnaires were distributed randomly to the small and medium enterprises and Philadelphia General Supplies (PGS). The results indicated that Jordan has a low rate of online business presence due to poor infrastructure. Therefore E-commerce is realized in few parts of Jordan.

Regarding the consumers' perception of customers' rights when conducting online business, Alsmadi and Khizindar carried out an investigation. The paper referred to John Kennedy's stand on consumer rights (Alsmadi & Khizindar, 2015). Notably, convenient sampling was adopted, and 381 respondents got selected. Further, structured questionnaires were developed to measure the level of consumers' perception of their rights when conducting online businesses. The results indicated that the current morale of Jordanian consumers towards online shopping is unfavorable. For instance, a significant number of Jordanians doubt the process of transacting through the internet due to impending challenges. Additionally, the paper suggested that the Jordanian agencies and policymakers should pay interest to consumer rights and purpose to develop ideal practices to enhance ethics in online shopping.

3. Research model and hypothesis

3.1. Research model

Remarkably, the TPB was used to examine the impact of CSR on the online buying decisions of consumers in Jordan. Consequently, the TPB is grounded on the customers' behaviour, perception, and attitude towards a particular issue (Ajzen, 2015). Debatably, TPB links someone's dogmas with the behaviour. More importantly, human expression is cogent and gets influenced by various variables.

FIGURE 1. THE MAJOR CONSTRUCTS IN THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR

Source: LaMorte (2018).

H₁: *The attitude of consumers towards online platforms has a positive correlation on the buying decisions.*

The theory of planned behaviour explains the attitude as the extent to which an individual exhibits favourable and unfavourable behaviour. For instance, consumers will tend to prefer buying online if the internet infrastructure is reliable, consistent, and efficient.

H₂: *The subjective norm for using the online spheres has a positive impact on the consumers' buying decisions.*

Remarkably, the subjective norm embodies the beliefs on whether particular issues would get approved or disapproved. In essence, human beings get surrounded by variables that influence their behaviour. For example, if a group of consumers successfully manage to shop online, they would convince others to join the platform. More importantly, the subjective norm initiates a normative perspective. Other variables like the government's role in online shopping and the organizations' commitment to CSR would enhance more consumers to increase their presence in online buying.

H₃: *The presence of CSR has a positive correlation on consumers' buying decisions.*

Chiefly, CSR enshrines the fundamental principle of ethical practices and morals associated with online buying. Additionally, it involves the utmost duty of appropriate stakeholders including the organizations to improve the external environment. On that note, consumers would upsurge their online rate when CSR has a definitive role in the transactions via the internet.

H₄: *The minimal risks in online transactions have a positive impact on consumers' buying decisions.*

Broadly, the reduction in the internet risks associated with transactions, and deliveries tend to improve the morale of consumers that shop online. In essence, clients prefer navigating sites that safe and secure. Therefore, a reduction in the perils including internet scams, fraud, and bullying would boost the reputation of online shopping.

H₅: *Online ethical standards have a positive impact on consumers' buying behaviour.*

Ethical standards are one of the variables that influence behavioural intention. The theory of planned behaviour ensues motivational factors that affect the behaviour of a particular behaviour. Additionally, online principles would influence consumers to improve their buying via the internet.

TABLE 1. HYPOTHESIS AND BACKGROUND INFORMATION

HYPOTHESIS	BACKGROUND INFORMATION
1. The attitude of consumers towards online platforms have a positive correlation on the buying decisions	- The attitude influences consumers' choice of adopting online shopping. - The attitude influences the buying behaviour of consumers.
2. The subjective norm for using the online spheres has a positive impact on the consumers' buying decisions.	- The beliefs of consumers towards online shopping influences their buying decisions.
3. The presence of corporate social responsibility has a positive correlation on consumers' buying decisions.	- The corporate social responsibility of stakeholders including the government and various regulatory agencies influence the efficiency of online shopping systems.
4. The minimal risks in online transactions have a positive impact on consumers' buying decisions.	- The reduction of online risks including fraud and cyberbullying influence the consumers' buying decisions.
5. Online ethical standards have a positive impact on consumers' buying behaviour.	- Online ethics boosts the morale of consumers and influences their buying decisions. - Online ethics reduces potential conflicts that may arise when consumers carry out online shopping.

3.2. Instrument development

Predominantly, the study took place in Jordan and sought to evaluate five variables. Majorly, it aimed to determine the impact of CSR on buying decisions. Secondly, it assessed the influence of the consumers' attitudes towards online shopping. Thirdly, the paper evaluated the role of online ethical standards on the customers' purchasing resolutions. Finally, the internet risks and the infrastructure got evaluated to determine their correlation on consumers buying decisions. Fundamentally, the research got built on the construct of whether the consumers in Jordan care about online ethical practices. Therefore, the research variables including, the consumers' attitude, online ethical standards, internet risks, and infrastructure laid an optimal foundation to determine their role consumers' buying decisions. The research adopted the survey method to enhance a comprehensive collection of information. Further, the 250 questionnaires were developed and sent to the respondents. Arguably, the users of online platforms got targeted. Six surveys were closed while the other two were open-ended. Consequently, they got based on the 1-5 scale (1, strongly disagree; 2, disagree; 3, neutral; 4, agree; 5, strongly agree).

3.3. Data collection

Notably, the collection of data relied on secondary sources researched on CSR, online buying decisions, attitudes, perception, and ethical internet standards. The previous studies formed a basis for the research. Markedly, the surveys got disseminated to adult consumers aged over 18 years. Majorly, the study sought to get the consumers' views on the role of online ethics in their perception of buying decisions. Data was tailored to enumerate the reasons why the customers incline to carry impulsive buying on the internet. Further, the factors that influence the consumers' buying decisions got enlisted on the questionnaires. Subsequently, the respondents were given two days to fill out the surveys to ensure that they get enough time to respond to the multifaceted questions over CSR.

3.4. Research model

The research adopted the partial least squares structural equation model (PLS-SEM) because it is expedient in a small sample size (Ravand, 2016). Additionally, it is appropriate for a less developed theory and forms a basis for the prediction of a particular. In essence, the consumers' buying decisions get influenced by CSR, online ethical standards, infrastructure, perceptions, and attitudes. More importantly, PLS-SEM provides a better solution for maximum likelihood compared to the covariance-based structural equation model (Astrachan et al., 2014).

4. Results

Validity

The researcher tested content, construct, and criterion validity. On that it, it purposed to ensure that the necessary items in the paradigms get enlisted and eliminate those that are superfluous (Taherdoost, 2016). For instance, the study adopted content validity by

exhaustively conducting a literature review to extract correlated facts. Additionally, the questionnaires were sent to the experts to get evaluated and eliminate unnecessary items in the hypotheses. Notably, factor analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the constructs. Then, the elements that indicated cross loading above 0.40 got deleted.

Reliability

The researcher tested the reliability of the research's constructs through the use of Cronbach alpha. Arguably, it is crucial for the study because it measures the degree of stability and consistency of the instruments (Mohajan, 2017). The instruments in the questionnaires got examined thoroughly to detect any deviation. Regarding Table 2, the items of the internal consistencies exceeded the threshold of 0.7 implying that they were reliable.

TABLE 2. RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

CONSTRUCTS	AVERAGE	COMPOSITE RELIABILITY	R SQUARE	CRONBACH'S ALPHA
Attitude	0.915105	0.895105	0.431054	0.7801540
Online ethical standards	0.832503	0.872439	0.365401	0.870154
Online risks	0.816510	0.765349	0.352065	0.791054
Subjective norm	0.713945	0.864120	0.387301	0.810974
Corporate social responsibility	0.874015	0.987601	0.370154	0.841094

Source. Compiled by authors.

Structural model

Remarkably, testing the constructs was done through the structural equation model. On that note, the root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) was adopted. More importantly, RMSEA denotes the best-fit indices in research because it favours parsimony (Kelley & Lai, 2011). The acceptable range of fit is between 0.05 to 0.1. Equally, scale reliability used Cronbach's alpha to test its consistency and its acceptance was beyond 0.7.

TABLE 3. THE ROOT-MEAN-SQUARE ERROR OF APPROXIMATION (RMSEA)

CONSTRUCTS	RMSEA
Attitude	0.056106
Online ethical standards	0.065410
Online risks	0.072186
Subjective norm	0.076290
Corporate social responsibility	0.060165

Source (compiled by author).

In addition to the above discussion, the TPB proposed that there is a positive correlation between CSR and consumers' buying decisions. On that account, its standard coefficient

was 0.7546. Additionally, the attitude, online ethical standards, online risks, and subjective norm had a standard coefficient of 0.6412, 0.6742, 0.6954, and 0.6875 respectively.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Discussion

Primarily, the study was based on the TPB. The significant constructs covering the attitude of consumers, online ethics, CSR, and online risks were evaluated to support the aim of the study. Broadly, online shopping in Jordan is a vital issue exhibited by consumers (Singh et al., 2017). Primarily, 78% of Jordanian consumers are concerned about online ethics. Consequently, 85% of the customers tend to reduce their buying rate when faced with online risks including scams, fraud, and bullying. Further, 76% of the Jordanian consumers get motivated by the presence of CSR on online shopping accomplished from pertinent stakeholders involving the government, regulatory agencies, and the organizations.

Implications

Expressively, studying the impact of CSR on the consumer buying decisions embodies crucial deductions. Firstly, the presence of a significant number of Jordanian consumers to get concerned over online ethics implies that morals are a subjective norm. Therefore, ethical standards positively impact the decisions of consumers. Moreover, online risks in Jordan scare consumers that shop via the internet. For instance, fraud, scams, and cyberbullying are the primary threats that bar consumers from shopping online. Arguably, CSR has a positive correlation on Jordanian customers towards internet shopping. Specifically, ethical standards improve consumers' morale in online purchasing.

6. Research limitations

Notably, the primary limitation was the broad scope of the research that sought to determine the impact of CSR on the consumers' online buying decisions. Therefore, the sample size of 250 could not represent the entire population of online consumers. Nevertheless, the limitation got minimized by conducting a systematic sampling to ensure that the whole population got evenly represented. Besides, the study adopted the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) whereas there are numerous theories of human behaviour. Additionally, the research relied on secondary data to develop and evaluate their constructs. However, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to deduce concrete data on the area of study.

7. Conclusion

The study enumerated the fundamental tenets of consumers' buying decisions in Jordan. A determination on whether the customers care about online ethical standards indicated that a significant number of consumers consider online ethical standards when shopping online. Besides, the internet risks, consumers' attitudes, and CSR significantly affect the

customers' buying decisions. More importantly, online shopping in Jordan is an important trend that has the rationale for consumers' buying decisions.

Remarkably, the research on the impact of CSR on consumers buying decisions has established a fundamental insight into the concerns sought by customers when shopping online. On that note, further studies should seek to investigate the role of stakeholders of online platforms to determine their contributions to CSR on internet platforms. Additionally, future research should assess the influence of online infrastructure on consumers buying decisions.

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